

CIRCE - WP5

Inclusive valorisation model for
controversial cultural heritage in the
Mediterranean Harbours and beyond

MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS Staff Exchanges (SE)
Project number: 101235092

Brand manual

Designer - Noemi Varricchio

APPRODI

Logo overview // -	[]
Grid System - Safe Area & Clear Space // -	[]
Graphic shapes & visual devices // -	[]
Color palette // -	[]
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Typography hierarchy & style // -	[]
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Research space setup and manifest // -	[]

Funded by
the European Union

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01

Visual concept- design approach

Modularità, frammenti, porzioni di mondo che sembrano disegnare **schemi più ampi**. Il logo proposto pone l'attenzione sulla natura in divenire del progetto. Un segno bold, una silhouette che costruisce un percorso, ma anche un'occhio per sottolineare la metodologia di ricerca. **Guardare e non vedere, per costruire nuove relazioni.**

Il logo costituisce un nucleo, un'iride, un punto di partenza e mai di fine, i confini si costruiscono man mano e sempre un po' più in là. Linee spesse e moderne permettono al segno di avere un'alta leggibilità in ogni sua declinazione sia cromatica che di dimensione. Nonostante lo spessore, la sua natura aperta rende il logo dinamico anche nelle future declinazioni e applicazioni.

Modularity, fragments, and portions of the world that appear to outline **broader patterns**. The proposed logo draws attention to the evolving nature of the project. A bold mark, a silhouette that constructs a trajectory, yet also an eye that underscores the research methodology. **To look without merely seeing, in order to build new relationships.**

The logo acts as a nucleus, an iris, a point of departure rather than an endpoint: its boundaries take shape gradually, extending ever further. Thick, contemporary lines ensure high legibility across all chromatic and dimensional adaptations. Despite its weight, the openness of the form lends the logo a dynamic quality, supporting future variations and applications.

Attraverso il prestito visuale del mondo dell'urbanistica, della segnaletica, riformuliamo un pensiero atto alla convergenza dell'attenzione.

Non più "attenzione" come pericolo ma come **spostamento del cono d'ombra**.

Solidi, balloons rigidi e dalle forme pungenti sottolineano e declinano il progetto, nella **molteplicità semiotica** che lo contraddistingue, ma anche silhouette dei pharmaka di Circe, per aprire la percezione a nuovi livelli di realtà

Siamo moltitudine tra porzioni di ombra e nuove attenzioni, intese come cura.

Non si ha la presunzione di riscrivere, nemmeno di rielaborare bensì la necessità di far riemergere una serie di **concatenazioni e ingranaggi nascosti** dalla scocca di una macchina storica, culturale atta all'avanzamento indisturbato e coadiuvato da uno sguardo colonizzatore.

Through the visual borrowing of urban planning and signage languages, we reformulate a mode of thinking oriented toward the convergence of attention.

Attention no longer as danger, but as a shift in the shadow cone.

Rigid, solid forms and sharp-edged balloons underscore and articulate the project within the semiotic multiplicity that defines it, while also recalling the silhouettes of Circe's pharmaka, opening perception to new layers of reality.

We exist as a multitude, suspended between areas of shadow and new forms of attention, understood as care.

There is no ambition to rewrite, nor even to rework; rather, there is the necessity to bring to the surface a set of chains and mechanisms concealed beneath the casing of a historical and cultural apparatus designed to advance undisturbed, supported by a colonizing gaze.

02

A set of shapes

a set of of shadows

#B5CD0D

#2DE4F4E

#333333

#FFFFFF

#3054A2

Palette cromatica dai toni mutati. I colori principali ossia il rosso e il verde sono frutto di un lavoro di selezione tra le cromie presenti sulle bandiere di tutti gli stati che sono coinvolti nel progetto.

A chromatic palette composed of muted tones. The primary colors, namely red and green, result from a careful selection process based on the chromatic nuances found in the national flags of all the countries involved in the project.

Correct variants

Incorrect usage

- []
- []
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Per garantire la leggibilità del logo la dimensione di stampa minima è di 3 cm con almeno 1 cm di spazio negativo lungo tutto il suo perimetro

To ensure optimal legibility, the logo must not be reproduced at a print size smaller than 3 cm and must be surrounded by a minimum of 1 cm of negative space along its entire perimeter.

Circe.EU
Europe, EU
MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS - Staff Exchanges (SE) - 6.762 followers
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Insight on Circe.EU
6 recent senior management hires
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy.

[+2](#)

Insight on The Partner

[See all details](#)

People Highlight
239 employees working in art and design
[+99](#)

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur

Primary Typeface -
Font: MERSAD- Bold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRST
UVWXYZ
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Font headline: Montserrat Underline

Regular- *abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz*
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789
*!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_*

Italic- *abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz*
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789
*!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_*

Semi-bold- ***abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz***
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Semi-bold italic- ***abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz***
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Black- ***abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz***
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Black italic- ***abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz***
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Font body: Indivisible

Regular- abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Light italic- *abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz*
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789
*!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_*

Italic- *abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz*
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789
*!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_*

Bold- **abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz**
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Arabic font: Noto sans Arabic

Light- ط ط ض ص ش س ز ر ذ د خ ح ج ث ت ب ا
ي و ه ن م ل ك ق ف غ ع
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Regular - ط ط ض ص ش س ز ر ذ د خ ح ج ث ت ب ا
ي و ه ن م ل ك ق ف غ ع
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Medium - ط ط ض ص ش س ز ر ذ د خ ح ج ث ت ب ا
ي و ه ن م ل ك ق ف غ ع ظ
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Bold- ط ط ض ص ش س ز ر ذ د خ ح ج ث ت ب ا
ي و ه ن م ل ك ق ف غ ع ظ
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Black - ض ص ش س ز ر ذ د خ ح ج ث ت ب ا
ي و ه ن م ل ك ق ف غ ع ظ
0123456789
!"£\$%&/()=?^*é\$°ç;:_

Focus group /
modularity +
ecofriendly

Research space setup // pag - X

